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**Experimental results of a measuring
base noise determination of the
marine gradientometer**

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РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ШУМА
ИЗМЕРИТЕЛЬНОЙ БАЗЫ МОРСКОГО ГРАДИЕНТОМЕТРА

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In paper are shown experimental results of magnetometric survey which were carrying out on board research vessels in different scientific expeditions.

Some type errors and dynamical noises which generated the marine gradientometer measuring base when it moving relatively to the ship's stern are considered here. The recommendation for its optimum calculation, filtration and compensation are given.

В работе представлены результаты экспериментальных исследований аппаратных шумов и динамических помех, генерируемых измерительной базой градиентометров различных типов, в процессе проведения морской магнитной съемки.

Даются рекомендации по их оптимальному учету, фильтрации и компенсации.

ИЗМИРАН, 1993 г.

Introduction.

The purpose of this work is demonstration of real value of the mean statistical noise of the gradientometric measuring base which generated a measuring base of the towed marine gradientometer when it moving relatively to the ship's stern.

It is known that a biggest part of the magnetic noise errors by the towing of the marine gradientometer vehicles with magnetic sensors is conditioned by outboard part of the marine gradientometer [see papers 1 - 11, 19 - 21]. This error was named as a deviation measuring bases error [1, 8, 11].

The practice of marine magnetic researches is shown that the noise component of the marine gradientometer deviation measuring bases error is depending on the towing parameters (amplitude and group velocity of choppiness, rolling and pitching of the ship, level of the vehicles depth motion, ship's velocity, influence of the keelwater tracks and so on) and from the ship's dimensions, from the value of the ship's magnetic momentum, from the length of towed cables. It be within the limits from 0,5 to 3,0 nT [3 - 8, 20, 22].

In this paper are demonstrating some experimental results of researches the some type errors in depending on change of the gradientometer measuring base or else on moving away it from the ship's stern for different types of the marine gradientometers [7 - 9].

The unique of the experiment was conditioned in the simultaneously using of four different types magnetic sensors which were towed in different distances (from 50

to 300 m) from the ship's stern.

Scheme of magnetometers equipment which were placed on board of the research vessel "Academik" is shown in Fig.1. More details about the marine magnetic survey by the program of the expedition EMINE-90 are discussed in papers [8 - 10].

Instruments.

During experimental work were used two towed marine proton precession magnetometers MBM-1 [12] and PMPM-01 (Institute of Oceanology, Varna, Bulgaria) [9] which had the limited length of towed cables 140 and 240 m and one towed quantum gradientometer KMB [4, 5, 13, 14] which used with a different variable cable length of its towed vehicles. Geomagnetic total field and its horizontal gradient were measured by protons and quantum magnetometers. In experiment was used the three-component magnetometer FM-2 [15] which was placed on shipboard and was measured three components of the geomagnetic field in the ship-coordinates. FM-2 is a fluxgate - type magnetometer. The three sensors of FM-2 assembled rectangular to each other are setting hard inside of the ship by special tripod. We also measured the ship's heading direction by gyrocompass and the ship's rolling, pitching angles by two one-component fluxgate magnetometers FMVS [16] which were registered by the special typerecorder and computer [17] every 1 or 2 s in real time scale (see Fig.1).

The accuracy of the fluxgate magnetometers FM-2 and FMVS was about 1,0 and 5,0 nT. The fluxgate magnetometers were magnetically compensated at every tack of magnetic survey. The accuracy of the proton precession magnetometers MBM-1 and PMPM-01 was about 0,1 nT. The

measuring cycle of the magnetometer MBM-1 was about 5 or 10 s and of the magnetometer PMPM-01 it was about 8 s.

The quantum differential magnetometer KMB had a different combinations of measuring cycles in diapason from 0,01 s to 10 s. The measuring accuracy of magnetometer KMB was a variable value from 0,001 nT to 1,0 nT and was depended upon of its measuring cycle. The accuracy of the magnetometer KMB during gradientometrical and methodical works was always about 0,1 nT with a measuring cycle 0,1 - 0,2 s. In such a cases the value of a mean calculating cycle of magnetometric and gradientometric data was regulated by special computer [13] within the limits from 1,0 to 300 s.

More details about the marine magnetometers and its data receiving are discussed by LYUBIMOV in papers [8 - 11] and in the papers [3 - 7, 18 and 19].

Depth data and data of navigation system GPS (velocity V_k and course φ_k of the ship and its spatial co-ordinates φ_k and λ_k) are obtained separately and later added to geomagnetic data. The navigation system GPS allowed us to obtain the navigation data every 2 s.

Experimental Investigations.

For the experimental estimation of influence of the ship's body magnetic momentum on the towed magnetic sensor were carried out a number of the next experiments.

The first experiment was consisted in estimation of the influence of the ship's body magnetic momentum on the towed magnetic's sensors on separately tacks of magnetic survey between two magnetic sensors.

During of an experiment one of the sensors was fixed in the distance about 170 m from the ship's stern and the

other sensor of the marine gradientometer KMB was moved and was fixed on different distances from the ship's stern (8, 9, 18). The maximum sensor's remoteness from the ship's stern was fixed about 5,5 its hull's length.

The second experiment was consisted the simultaneous measurement of the magnetic sensors course deviation for all four magnetic sensors which were towing on different distances from the ship's stern and the synchronous measurement of the magnetic field value on shipboard by three-component fluxgate magnetometer FM-2 (8, 9).

The third experiment was consisted the simultaneous measurement of the magnetic field gradient in towed vehicles by the measuring base $\Delta l = 120$ m (channel G) and perpendicular of the ship's course component of magnetic field on its board by fluxgate magnetometer FM-2 (channel X). In this experiment was used quantum differential magnetometer KMB which had the cycle of the magnetic field registration about 0,1 s.

The fourth experiment was included the simultaneous measurement of the horizontal magnetic field gradient between different pair of magnetic sensors which were towed on the different measuring bases and which were towed in different distances from the ship's stern. The measuring cycle of the quantum magnetometer KMB in this case was used $t = 0,1$ s. Proton precession magnetometers MBM-1 and PMPM-01 had the measuring cycles $t = 10$ s and $t = 8$ s accordingly.

The fifth experiment was consisted of the gradientometer measuring base noise researching on it different length by a different value of towing velocity and choppiness force. We were carrying out our investigations on different ship's tacks and courses and we were taking control of the ship's velocity and its yawing on

the course by the ship's computer too.

The sixth experiment was included the gradientometer measuring base noise researches when the measuring base had of the same length and when it had a different remoteness from the ship's stern. It was estimating the noise value of the same measuring bases of quantum and proton gradientometers when they were towing simultaneously and it was estimating the keelwater track influence on the results of a measurements.

The seventh experiment was consisted of the optimum measuring time interval selection on a different courses of marine magnetic survey for marine gradientometer which was permitted us at much as possible to decrease the error's value which was connected with the noise of towing measuring base. Special computer [13] which was linking to the output of quantum differential magnetometer KMS (see Fig.1) was using in this experiment.

Results and Discussion.

Results of the experimental measurement of the ship's body magnetic momentum influence on the towed magnetic sensors in one of the tacks during marine magnetic survey are shown in Fig.2. The length of the towed cables (l_c) is normalized to the ship hull's length here. The length of the r/v "Academik" from the bow to the stern was equaled about $l_k = 55$ m. It is noticeable that the value of the ship's magnetic momentum influence on the magnetic sensors in towed vehicles is depend on its remoteness from the ship's stern as about $1/l_c^3$.

Experimental researches results of the ship's magnetic course deviation which were observed on shipboard and the results of the simultaneous measurement of the

magnetic sensors course deviation for all magnetic sensors in towed vehicles on different distances ($l_c = 50, 100, 140, 170$ and 240 m) from the ship's stern are shown in Fig.3. It is clear that the maximum influence of the ship's magnetic momentum on the towed magnetic sensors is expressed in northward and southward direction for all magnetic sensors even if the towed cable length is in 4 - 5 once more than the ship hull's length.

Results of the ship's course magnetic deviation measurement which was observed on its board and results of the synchronous simultaneous measurement of the real difference magnetic course deviation characteristic ΔG of marine gradientometers which had the same measuring base length $\Delta l = 50$ m on different distances 50 m and 170 m from the ship's stern are shown in Fig.4. It is clear good that the primary ship's magnetic momentum influence on the gradientometer's measuring bases is expressed on northward and southward direction too (see Fig.3). Should the gradientometer measuring base remoteness distance to increase in 3,5 once more from the ship's stern, the ship's magnetic momentum influence to it would to decrease about halve.

Fragments of the horizontal magnetic field gradient recording by marine gradientometer on the measuring base $\Delta l = 70$ m in separately different courses of the magnetic survey are shown in Fig.5 and Fig.6. The nearest vehicle of the marine gradientometer, is being from the ship's stern in the distance about two its hull's length ($l_c = 100$ m) here. The towing parameters (towing velocity V_k and sea choppiness) in both instances are equally.

One can easily see in Fig.5 that the noise mean amplitude value of the gradientometer measuring base is differing about twice on the opposite courses ($\varphi_k = 75^\circ$ and 255°) of the gradientometric survey. The noise mean ampli-

tude value of the marine gradientometer measuring base which is conditioned by the ship's magnetic momentum influence is differ on different tacks and its value is being within the limits from 1,5 - 2,0 nT to 3,0 - 3,5 nT (see Fig.6).

Fragment of the magnetic field gradient recording on the perpendicular courses ($\Phi_k = 150^\circ$ and 240°) of the magnetic survey when the nearest vehicle is towing in the distance 50 m from the ship's stern is shown in Fig.7. The length of the gradientometer measuring base is $\Delta l = 20$ m here and the measuring cycle of the gradientometer is 0,1 s. To increase the measuring accuracy we are middlized the measuring data in the time base 30 s here. One can easily see that the gradientometer measuring base noise value on different courses is conditioned by different ship's magnetic momentum influence is differ almost twice even if we are middlized the measuring results on the long time interval.

The experimental researches results of the marine gradientometer measuring base noise on separately tacks of the magnetic survey when the length of the gradientometer measuring bases are nearly equal $\Delta l = 50$ m and 120 m are shown in Fig.8. The nearest vehicle was towing in the distance $l_c = 50$ m from the ship's stern here. One can see well if the measuring base length Δl increase in about 2,5 once the mean amplitude of the gradientometer measuring base noise increase proportionally too. The mean amplitude noise increasing is less noticeably on course $\Phi_k = 335^\circ$ because the ship's magnetic momentum influence is a very big on the nearest towed sensor of the marine gradientometer.

Fragment of the simultaneous measurement of the magnetic field's components X, Y and Z on shipboard and of the magnetic field horizontal gradient G on the measuring

base $\Delta l = 120$ m is shown in Fig.9. The marine gradientometer measuring base was towing from the ship's stern in the distance about 50 m. The towing velocity was 5 kn and the value of sea choppiness force was 1 - 2 during an experiment. One can see that the high-frequency noise of the gradientometer measuring base has identical period if it compare with X-component of magnetic field record on shipboard. The calculations we made on basis a lot of statistical material are showed that the main period of the gradientometer measuring base noise was equaled $T_n = 5,31$ s with a standard deviation $G_n = \pm 0,08$ s. The measuring base noise amplitude changing is being in the limits from 0,2 to 0,8 nT and it is good co-ordinated with X-component oscillations which were measured on shipboard.

Fragment of the simultaneous recording of geomagnetic total field B_T , its horizontal gradient G on measuring base $\Delta l = 120$ m in towed vehicles and X-component of magnetic field which is measuring on shipboard when sea choppiness force is mount 4 - 5 is shown in Fig.10. One can see well that the ship's magnetic momentum influence on the magnetic field gradient measuring results is changing if sea choppiness force is rising. The mean amplitude of the gradientometer measuring base noise increase roughly in 3 - 5 once against the data in Fig.9. It is clear from Fig.10 the noise which generate a present marine gradientometer measuring base can separate conditionally into three categories: high-frequency noise with amplitude about 2 - 5 nT which are conditioned by ship's rolling and pitching in motion, low-frequency noise with period 60 - 90 s and amplitude about 5 - 10 nT which are conditioned by sea choppiness force and low-frequency noise with period more than 400 s which are conditioned by roving of the ship's automatic pilot and by its drifting from the course.

Results of the horizontal magnetic field course gradient measurement between five different pairs of four magnetic sensors which are towing simultaneously during an experiment are shown in Fig.11 (curves 3 - 7). Curves analysis of the simultaneous gradient recording between magnetic sensors of different types is shown that the least value of high-frequency noise which generate gradientometer measuring base had a pair of quantum sensors 1 and 3 (curve 4 in Fig.11) and which had standard deviation from mean value $G_n = \pm 0,41$ nT. It is in 3 once less than between a pair of sensors 3 and 4 (curve 5) which had the same measuring base $\Delta l = 70$ m and which had remoteness twice as much from the ship's stern. The most gradientometer measuring base noise ($G_n = \pm 1,49$ nT) are to be observed by a pair of proton precession sensors 2 and 4 (curve 6) which had measuring cycles accordingly 10 s and 8 s and which had the gradientometer measuring base length $\Delta l = 100$ m.

Experimental results of the noise mean amplitude value which generated a measuring base of quantum marine gradientometer when it towed with different velocity (V_k) are shown in Fig.12. Researches are carrying out by the ship's towing velocities in the limits from 2 till 8 knots by sea choppiness force 5 and when the ship is rolling. Results of it measurement by the towing velocity $V_k = 8$ kn are shown in Fig.8b too.

As a result of data analysis is obvioued that a towing velocity decreasing reduced to increasing of noise mean amplitude value which generated a measuring base of marine gradientometer. Therefore, it was correct to show in papers [6 and 7], if you use marine gradientometer with two towing cables and vehicles it must not have towing velocity its measuring base less than 6 - 7 knots.

Fragments of the horizontal course gradient record:

on separately tracks of magnetic survey when sea choppiness force had different value and the gradientometer measuring base length was $\Delta l = 20$ m are shown in Fig.13 and Fig.14. The ship's velocity (V_k) and its yawing on the course (φ_k) were controlling by ship's computer. The noise mean amplitude value which generated marine gradientometer measuring base on the distance 50 m from the ship's stern exceedn't 1,0 - 1,3 nT here.

Fragments of real recording of sea choppiness force influence on the noise mean amplitude value which were generated the marine gradientometer measuring base and each of gradientometer towed sensors during marine magnetic survey are shown in Fig.15, Fig.16, Fig.17 and Fig.18. One can see well that magnetic field records in the nearest vehicles of marine gradientometers (see curves 1 in Fig.15 and Fig.16) are complicated more high-frequency noises which had the most noise amplitude value too than in the distant vehicles (see curves 2). Amplitude value of this noise depend with the ship's moving direction as regards on sea choppiness direction and its amplitude. One can see good in Fig.15 the noise main period and the noise amplitude value which was generated the gradientometer measuring base and which were registrated in each of towed vehicles of marine gradientometer by rapid magnetic field recording when the ship sailed by the wind. In that case the gradientometer measuring cycle was about 0,1 s. The noise mean amplitude (ΔB_d) of the nearest towed vehicle is about in 2,5 once more (see curve 1 in Fig.15) than of the distant vehicle and the noise mean period (ΔT_d) is equally about 0,4 s. Results of the noise mean amplitude value researches of the nearest marine quantum gradientometer sensor were expressing at the magnetic field recording and which were depending on sea choppiness force are shown in Fig.17. The

records were made by the same towing velocity (V_k) of vehicle in all cases when the ship's moving direction and sea choppiness direction are coincided [22]. It is necessary to note here if the choppiness force is changing from 2 to 7 the noise mean amplitude value (ΔB_d) of the nearest marine gradientometer sensor is increasing in about 5 - 6 once and it is reaching the value 3,0 - 3,5 nT (see papers [18 and 22]). These results had a good agreement with results which were shown in Fig.18 where it was shown the noise amplitude value increasing in 2,0 - 2,5 once on the gradientometer measuring base $\Delta l = 120$ m if sea choppiness force is increasing from 3 to 5. One can see well here that results in Fig.18 are having a good coincidence with data in Fig.4 too.

Real measuring base noise records of the marine proton gradientometer which were obtained during marine gradientometric survey in the Barents Sea are shown in Fig.19 and Fig.20 (see curves 1). These records were made by FILIN [6] during the 19-th cruise of the r/v "Professor Shtokhman" which had its hull's length $l_k = 69$ m. Marine proton gradientometer DPM [7] had the measuring base length $\Delta l = 150$ m which was towing in the distance $l_c = 300$ m from the ship's stern here. The measuring cycle of the proton gradientometer DPM was equal to 5 s in this case. It is see good in Fig.19 and Fig.20 that the noise mean amplitude value of the proton gradientometer measuring base is enough to big yet and it value is equal to 1,0 - 1,5 nT by it remoteness from the ship's stern on about 4,3 its hull's length. These data are coincided well with the proton gradientometer data which were shown in Fig.11 (curve 6, sensors 2 and 4). Results of the course gradient data optimum filtration which were made by special computer when it was processing the real observed data are shown in Fig.19 and Fig.20 too (curves 2).

Comparative results of the noises real amplitude values which generated identical measuring bases $\Delta l = 100$ m of proton (curve 1) and quantum (curve 2) towed gradientometers on one of the courses ($\varphi_k = 330^\circ$) of marine magnetic survey are shown in Fig.21. Results of the horizontal course gradient data calculating with the help of special computer which was linking to output of quantum gradientometer KMB (see Fig.1) on the time interval 75 s are shown here too (curve 3). One can see well that the noise mean amplitude value for the proton gradientometer measuring base is in 2,0 - 2,5 once more then it value for the quantum gradientometer even if it remoteness from the ship's stern will be twice more.

Fragment of the real simultaneous magnetic field record of the towed quantum gradientometer which had the measuring base length $\Delta l = 70$ m and which was towing it with velocity $V_k = 8$ kn is shown in Fig 12. Record of the magnetic field course gradient (G) is complicated by low-frequency noises here which had a main period is depending from sea choppiness force and which had the mean amplitude value about 1,5 - 2,0 nT and by high-frequency noises which had the mean amplitude value about 0,2 - 0,4 nT which depended on the ship's yawing on the course. One can see well that the nature of the gradient record (G) is forming in general with a magnetic field record of the nearest sensor (B_{r2}) which is towing in the distance $l_c = 100$ m from the ship's stern, The noise mean amplitude value which was registrated by the distant sensor of marine gradientometer was exceedn't 1,0 nT in this case.

During marine magnetic survey we are using the methods of digital data filtration and the methods of data meaning in different time interval bases for the course gradient measuring accuracy increasing here. It was allowed to reduce the noises which was generated the

marine gradientometer measuring base approximately in 5 - 10 once. Results of marine gradientometer data digital filter modelling on different measuring time intervals and time bases are shown in Fig.23, Fig.24 and Fig.25. Real magnetic horizontal course gradient record on the measuring base $\Delta l = 20$ m when the quantum gradientometer measuring cycle is equal to 1 s is shown in Fig.23 (curve 1). Curves 2, 3 and 4 are shown results of data meaning from output of special computer here when the time meaning intervals of data processing was equally 30, 60 and 300 s accordingly. Data meaning during time interval 5 min (see curve 4) was allowed to reduce visible the error which was linking with the gradientometer measuring base noise when it was towing from the ship's stern in the distance less than one its hull's length.

Fragment of magnetic field record in both towed vehicles of marine quantum gradientometer on one of the courses of marine magnetic survey when the nearest vehicle was towing in the distance $l_c = 70$ m from the ship's stern is shown in Fig.24. The measuring base between both magnetic sensors is equally $\Delta l = 100$ m here. The course horizontal gradient record (B) between magnetic sensors was made from output of special computer which used the data meaning time interval 1 min. One can see well that the magnetic field gradient record (B) is in 10 once more sensitivity than the records of the separate sensors (B_{r_1}) and (B_{r_2}) and it isn't complicated by high-frequency noises as a record of the nearest sensor (B_{r_1}) which has the noise mean amplitude value about 2,0 - 2,5 nT.

Fragment of magnetic field horizontal course gradient record when the marine gradientometer measuring base $\Delta l = 70$ m is towing in keelwater ship's track is shown in Fig.25. The noise mean amplitude value of the gradientometer measuring base is reached 4,5 - 5,0 nT

(curve 1) when the towing velocity (V_k) is equally 8 kn here. When we put into practice data meaning in different measuring time intervals, for example, $t = 30$ s (curve 2) and $t = 75$ s (curve 3) we get an appreciable diminution of the gradientometer measuring base noise mean amplitude value even when it has short remoteness (100 m) from the ship's stern.

To conduct a correct comparative analysis of the measuring base noise error for different types of marine gradientometers we constructed amplitude characteristics of the mean statistical noise $A = |G_{B_d}/\Delta l|$ which were normalized to the gradientometer measuring base length Δl and which are shown in Fig.2b. The sign "minus" on the ordinate axis shows on the gradientometer measuring base position relatively of the supporting magnetic sensor here.

As a result of experimental data analysis is obviated that the proton gradientometer measuring base had the mean statistical noise amplitude value twice as much in comparison with the quantum gradientometer measuring base even if it has greater remoteness from the ship's stern.

Conclusion.

On the grounds of experimental findings we can make a number of recommendations which are directed on rise of gradient magnetic field accuracy measurement in marine conditions.

The remoteness value from the ship's stern of the nearest marine gradientometer sensor must be no less than six ship hull's length.

Before the works it is necessary to determine the

real difference deviation characteristic of the gradientometer measuring base in every concrete case.

The time of the marine gradientometer measuring cycle must be in 5 - 10 once less or, at least, it must be divisible by the high-frequency noise period which generate the gradientometer measuring base when it is towing by ship.

It is necessary to put into practice the digital data filtration methods and the methods of data meaning in different time intervals which are selecting optimally in the process of work and which are connected with concrete conditions and parameters of the marine gradientometer measuring base towing.

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Figure Captions.

Fig.1. Scheme of magnetometers and of the other equipment which were placed on board of the r/v "Academik and which were used in the process of work. There are showed the length of cables together with vehicles which were towing during an experiment.

PMPM-01 and MBM-1 - proton precession magnetometers;

FMV8 and FM-2 - fluxgate magnetometers;

KMB - quantum differential magnetometer.

Fig.2. Experimental results of the ship's body magnetic momentum influence on the towed magnetic sensors in one of the tacks during marine magnetic survey when the sensors towing distance from the ship's stern was different.

l_k - the ship hull's length;

l_{c_1} and l_{c_2} - the length of the towed cables of first and second magnetic sensors;

Δl - the gradiometer measured base length.

Fig.3. Experimental researches results of the magnetic

course deviation on shipboard and of the magnetic sensors course deviation for all magnetic sensors in towed vehicles at different distances ($l_c = 50, 100, 140, 170$ and 240 m) from the ship's stern.

Diagram scale ΔB_T : 5 mT/cm - on shipboard (shade line);

10 nT/cm - for towed sensors.

Fig.4. Determination results of the magnetic course deviation (ΔB_T) on shipboard and of the real difference magnetic course deviation characteristics (ΔG) of marine gradientometer which had the same measured base length ($\Delta l = 50$ m) at distances 50 and 170 m from the ship's stern.

Diagram scales: $\Delta B_T - 5$ mT/cm;

$\Delta G - 5$ nT/cm.

Fig.5. Fragments of the horizontal magnetic field gradient (G) records by marine gradientometer KMB on opposite courses ($\varphi_k = 75^\circ$ and 255°) of magnetic survey when the measured base length is equally $\Delta l = 70$ m. The distance of the gradientometer measured base from the ship's stern is equally 100 m.

Fig.6. Fragments of the horizontal magnetic field gradient (G) records by marine gradientometer on the measured base $\Delta l = 70$ m in separately different courses ($\varphi_k = 75^\circ, 150^\circ, 255^\circ$ and 330°) of magnetic survey.

Fig.7. Fragment of the horizontal magnetic field gradient (G) record by quantum marine gradientometer KMB in perpendicular courses ($\varphi_k = 150^\circ$ and 240°) of magnetic survey. The nearest sensor was towing in the

distance 50 m from the ship's stern here. The gradientometer measuring base length was $\Delta l = 20$ m in that case. Data are obtained from output of special computer by the meaning time interval 30 s.

Fig.8. Fragments of the marine gradientometer measuring base noise determination on separately tracks of magnetic survey. The nearest magnetic sensor was towing in the distance 50 m from the ship's stern line. The gradientometer measuring base length was equally $\Delta l = 50$ m (a) and $\Delta l = 120$ m (b) here.

Fig.9. Fragment of simultaneous measurement of the magnetic field's components (X, Y and Z) on shipboard by fluxgate magnetometer FM-2 and of the magnetic field horizontal gradient (G) on measuring base $\Delta l = 120$ m by quantum marine gradientometer KMB when it was towing in the distance 50 m from the ship's stern.

Fig.10. Fragment of simultaneous record of geomagnetic total field (Br), its horizontal gradient (G) on measuring base ($\Delta l = 120$ m) in towed vehicles and record one of magnetic field component (X) on shipboard in one of the courses of magnetic survey. The gradientometer measuring base length is equally 120 m here.

Fig.11. Results of the horizontal magnetic field course gradient records between five different pairs of four magnetic sensors which were towing simultaneously during an experiment (curves 3 - 7). Records of ship's course direction (θ_k) and of geomagnetic total field (Br) in one of the towed vehicles are

also shown accordingly by curves 1 and 2 here.

Fig.12. Experimental results of the noise mean amplitude value determination which generated a measuring base ($\Delta l = 120$ m) of quantum gradientometer KMB when it towed with different velocity ($V_k = 2, 3 - 4$ and 5 kn). The nearest magnetic sensor was towing in the distance 50 m from the ship's stern during an experiment.

Fig.13. Fragment of simultaneous record of geomagnetic total field (B_r) in different scales (scales $B_r = 1 : 1$ and $1 : 10$) and of horizontal magnetic field course gradient (G) on measuring base $\Delta l = 20$ m together with records of the ship's course direction changing (φ_k) and of the ship's velocity changing (V_k) during an experiment when choppiness force was equally $2 - 3$.

Fig.14. Fragment of simultaneous record of horizontal magnetic field course gradient (G) by measuring base length $\Delta l = 20$ m together with records of the ship's course direction changing (φ_k) and of the ship's velocity changing (V_k) when choppiness force was equally $1 - 2$. The nearest magnetic sensor was towing in the distance 50 m from the ship's stern here.

Fig.15. Experimental record of the noise mean amplitude value (ΔB_d) which were measured by each of quantum gradientometer magnetic sensors on different distances from the ship's stern during marine magnetic survey. The nearest and the distant magnetic sensors were towing in the distance 100

and 170 m accordingly from the ship's stern here.

Fig.16. Experimental record of the magnetic total field (Br_1 and Br_2) by each of quantum gradientometer magnetic sensors which were towing in different distances 100 and 180 m from the ship's stern.

Fig.17. Experimental results of the noise mean amplitude value determination in depending on sea choppiness force. Records were made by measurement of magnetic total field in the nearest vehicle of marine quantum gradientometer when it was towing in the distance 100 m from the ship's stern.

Fig.18. Experimental records of the marine gradientometer measuring base noise amplitude value in depending on sea choppiness force when the gradientometer measuring base length was equally $\Delta l = 120$ m. The nearest gradientometer magnetic sensor was towing in the distance 50 m from the ship's stern here.

Fig.19. Real measuring base noise record (curve 1) of the marine proton gradientometer DPM during marine gradientometric survey in the Barents Sea. Record was made by FILIN during the 19-th cruise of the r/y "Professor Stokhman". Curve 2 shows the result of the course gradient data optimum filtration by computer.

Fig.20. Real measured data (curve 1) and optimum filtration data by computer (curve 2) of magnetic field gradient (G) during marine gradientometric survey in Barents Sea. The proton gradientometer measuring base length was equally $\Delta l = 150$ m in

that case and it was towing in the distance 300 m from the ship's stern,

Fig.21. Comparative results of the noises real amplitude value which generated identical measuring bases ($\Delta l = 100$ m) of proton (curve 1) and quantum (curve 2) towed gradientometers on one of the courses ($\varphi_k = 330^\circ$) of marine magnetic survey. Result of data meaning on the time interval $t = 75$ s by computer is shown by curve 3 here.

Fig.22. Fragment of simultaneous magnetic total field record by towed magnetic sensors (Br_1 and Br_2) together with record of magnetic field course gradient (G) on the measuring base ($\Delta l = 70$ m) of marine quantum gradientometer KMB during marine magnetic survey.

Fig.23. Example of marine gradientometer data processing by special computer during marine magnetic survey. It is shown the example of optimum meaning measuring time interval ($t = 30, 60$ and 300 s) modelling for marine gradientometer measuring base $\Delta l = 20$ m when it was towing in the distance 50 m from the ship's stern (curves 2 - 4). Record of real measuring magnetic field horizontal course gradient (G) by measuring cycle $t = 1$ s from marine gradientometer output is shown by curve 1 here.

Fig.24. Fragment of real magnetic field record by marine quantum gradientometer KMB on one of the courses of marine magnetic survey when it measuring base $\Delta l = 100$ m was towing in the distance 70 m from

the ship's stern. The measuring cycle of both gradientometer measuring channels (Br_1 and Br_2) is equally $t = 1$ s by analog record scale 10 nT/cm. The measuring cycle of gradient channel (G) is equally $t = 1$ min by analog record scale 1 nT/cm.

Fig.25. Fragment of marine gradientometer data processing by special computer during marine magnetic survey when the gradientometer measuring base $\Delta l = 70$ m was towing in keelwater ship's track. It is shown data meaning in measuring time interval $t = 30$ s (curve 2) and $t = 75$ s (curve 3). Curve 1 is shows real horizontal magnetic course gradient record here.

Fig.26. Experimental amplitude characteristics of the mean statistical noise of marine gradientometer measuring base length Δl which was towing from the ship's stern for different types of marine gradientometers (lc - remoteness distance of nearest marine gradientometer sensor from the ship's stern).

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Fig.3.

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